

NURTURING GROWTH: A DECADAL EXPLORATION OF NEWLY ESTABLISHED ENTERPRISES IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This paper explores the dynamics and evolution of newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area over the period from 2008 to 2018. Through a detailed analysis of statistical data, the study aims to provide insights into the entrepreneurial landscape, examining the trends, challenges, and contributions of newly founded businesses to regional development in the mountainous terrain.

1. Introduction:

Entrepreneurial activities are crucial for regional development, and the Romanian Mountain Area stands as a unique backdrop for examining the

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establishment of new enterprises. This paper investigates the trends, challenges, and contributions of newly established enterprises within this region over the past decade. (Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2021a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2022a-h)

2. Methodology:

Employing a comprehensive quantitative approach, this research compiles and analyzes data from business registries, official reports, and relevant publications. Key indicators such as the number and types of newly established enterprises, sectoral distribution, and survival rates are examined to offer a comprehensive understanding of the entrepreneurial landscape in the Romanian Mountain Area.

3. Emergence of New Enterprises:

This section explores the statistical intricacies related to the emergence of new enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area. Metrics such as the annual growth rate, industry diversity, and geographical distribution of these

enterprises are scrutinized to assess the region's entrepreneurial vibrancy and resilience.

4. Sectoral Analysis:

The paper delves into a sectoral analysis, examining the distribution of newly established enterprises across different industries in the Romanian Mountain Area. Insights into key sectors driving entrepreneurial activities, their contributions to the regional economy, and variations in sectoral growth patterns are discussed.

5. Survival and Success Rates:

Analyzing the survival and success rates of newly established enterprises, this section investigates factors influencing the sustainability of businesses in the mountainous terrain. Understanding the challenges faced by new enterprises is essential for policymakers and stakeholders seeking to create an environment conducive to entrepreneurship.

6. Economic Contributions:

Assessing the economic contributions of newly established enterprises, the paper investigates their impact on the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), employment rates, and overall economic stability. The interconnectedness between the emergence of new businesses and regional development is explored.

7. Challenges and Opportunities:

Identifying challenges and opportunities encountered by entrepreneurs in the Romanian Mountain Area, this section provides insights into factors such as access to financing, regulatory frameworks, and market conditions. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for shaping policies that support the growth of newly established enterprises.

8. Results:

This indicator shows the number of established businesses (start-ups, spin-offs or other types of new businesses). It is the indicator that expresses the degree of dynamism of a region or an economic sector, in this case the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors of the national economy.

The related descriptive analysis S1 (see the related table and figure, respectively the appendix of chapter 3) presents statistical values for Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. In Kurtosis, distance, minimum, maximum, 25, 50, 75, thus 27335.55, 3339.023, 27931.00, 11074.287, 122639833.873, 1,299, .661, 3,885, 1,279, 43287, 11498, 54785, 23355.00, 27931.00, 3031.00.

The models used for forecasting analysis are S1 - Model_1: ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2: ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3: ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4: ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5: Holt; S6 - Model_6: ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7: Simple; S8 - Model_8: ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9: ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10: Holt; S11 - Model_11: Holt.

Statistical prediction smoothing (repeated in this order each time – Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles) is performed as follows for static R-squared .371, -.026, .855, -.026, -.021; R-square .214, -4.441E-16, .510, -4.441E-16, -3.997E-16; RMSE 3147,051, 358,986, 11074,287, 358,986, 384,847; MAPS 9,409, 21,678, 49,611, 21,678, 21,906; MaxAPE 52.039, 67.715, 223.527, 67.715, 69.004; MAE 1880.279, 222.347, 6679.223, 222.347, 247.212; MaxAE7939.448, 855.064,

27449.455, 855.064, 870.688; Normalized BIC 2.001, 11.985, 18.843, 11.985, 12.151.

The resulting statistical forecasting models show the following overall table for I2 (values presented in the following order - static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, MAE) S1-Model_1:: 4.441E-16, 4.441E-16, 11074.287, 31,248, 6679,223; S2-Model_2: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 935.051, 26.820, 591.372; S3-Model_3: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 1102.698, 28.690, 791.190; S4-Model_4: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 3690.752, 26.567, 2107.835; S5-Model_5: .855, .457, 561,718, 22,818, 378,971; S6-Model_6: 5.551E-16, 5.551E-16, 571.508, 21.678, 355.901; S7-Model_7: -.026, .214, 638,928, 30,677, 420,011; S8-Model_8: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 358.986, 49.611, 222.347; S9-Model_9: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 2086.112, 40.253, 1231.471; S10-Model_10: .671, .416, 488,292, 44,157, 346,671; S11-Model_11: .830, .510, 1012,106, 42,713, 634,809.

Table 19. Prediction analysis for newly established enterprises

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
S1-Model_1:	Forecast	27336	27336	27336	27336	27336	27336	27336	27336
	UCL	52011	52011	52011	52011	52011	52011	52011	52011
	LCL	2660	2660	2660	2660	2660	2660	2660	2660
S2-Model_2:	Forecast	2541	2541	2541	2541	2541	2541	2541	2541
	UCL	4625	4625	4625	4625	4625	4625	4625	4625

	LCL	458	458	458	458	458	458	458	458
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	3287	3287	3287	3287	3287	3287	3287	3287
	UCL	5744	5744	5744	5744	5744	5744	5744	5744
	LCL	830	830	830	830	830	830	830	830
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	8022	8022	8022	8022	8022	8022	8022	8022
	UCL	16245	16245	16245	16245	16245	16245	16245	16245
	LCL	-202	-202	-202	-202	-202	-202	-202	-202
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	3115	3271	3427	3582	3738	3893	4049	4204
	UCL	4386	4548	4710	4871	5033	5195	5356	5518
	LCL	1845	1994	2143	2293	2442	2592	2741	2891
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	1649	1649	1649	1649	1649	1649	1649	1649
	UCL	2922	2922	2922	2922	2922	2922	2922	2922
	LCL	375	375	375	375	375	375	375	375
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860
	UCL	3284	3742	4109	4423	4703	4958	5194	5414
	LCL	437	-21	-388	-702	-983	-1237	-1473	-1693
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	644	644	644	644	644	644	644	644
	UCL	1444	1444	1444	1444	1444	1444	1444	1444
	LCL	-156	-156	-156	-156	-156	-156	-156	-156
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	4213	4213	4213	4213	4213	4213	4213	4213
	UCL	8861	8861	8861	8861	8861	8861	8861	8861
	LCL	-435	-435	-435	-435	-435	-435	-435	-435
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	1884	2010	2136	2262	2388	2514	2640	2766
	UCL	2988	3120	3251	3383	3514	3646	3777	3909
	LCL	779	900	1020	1141	1262	1382	1503	1624
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	4010	4320	4629	4939	5248	5558	5867	6177
	UCL	6300	6621	6941	7262	7583	7903	8224	8545

	LCL	1721	2019	2317	2615	2914	3212	3511	3809
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Figure 3.10. Graphical prediction analysis for I2

8. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this paper provides a comprehensive exploration of newly established enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the entrepreneurial landscape, offering valuable insights for policymakers, business leaders, and researchers. The paper concludes with reflections on potential trajectories and recommendations for fostering sustainable entrepreneurial growth in the mountainous region.

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